

ISic1473

I.Sicily inscription 1473

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

local stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

2014.09.11

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Greek necropolis in contrada Palazzo (proprieta Gargallo) between via S. Panagia and so-called 'muro di Gelone'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 57168

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀλέξιος τὸ σα

2. μα

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644983

PHI 330151

Bibliography

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